

COMPRESSIVE BEHAVIOUR OF PVC FOAM IN ELEVATED TEMPERATURE USING DIGITAL IMAGE CORRELATION AND A MODIFIED ARCAN FIXTURE

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Keywords: *Compressive behavior of foam materials, elevated temperature, modified Arcan fixture, DIC, nonlinear finite element analysis*

1 Introduction

Polymer foam cored sandwich structures are often subjected elevated temperatures. The mechanical properties of polymer foam cores degrade significantly with elevated temperatures, and significant changes in the properties occur well within the operating range of temperatures. Furthermore sandwich core materials may experience multidirectional mechanical stress states. Therefore, proper design of sandwich structures requires the characterization of the core material response under multi-directional stress states. Previously, the Arcan test rig has been used to measure bidirectional properties of polymer foams used for sandwich core materials, especially in the bidirectional tensile-shear stress region [1].

Fig. 1: MAF fixture used for compressive characterisation of Divinycell H100 [2].

A modified Arcan fixture (MAF) has been developed to characterize polymer foam materials with respect to their tensile, compressive, shear and bidirectional mechanical properties at room and at elevated temperatures, and including the elastic coefficients and the full nonlinear stress-strain response to failure [2].

The MAF, which is shown in Fig. 1, enables the realization of pure compression or high compression to shear bidirectional loading conditions that are not possible with conventional Arcan fixtures. The MAF is attached to a standard universal test machine equipped with an environmental chamber using specially designed grips that do not constrain the specimen rotation, and hence reduces parasitic effects due to misalignment.

2 Objectives, experimental and computational procedures

2.1 Objectives

The work presented in this paper focuses on the experimental characterisation of cross linked Divinycell H100 PVC foam material from room temperature to 85°C when subjected to pure compressive loading. As established in [2] and [3] Divinycell PVC foams are orthotropic, and the full orthotropic behaviour is characterised accordingly. The MAF fixture [2] was used for the testing, and the deformation and straining of the foam core was measured using digital image correlation (DIC).

2.2 Experimental procedure

Compressive testing of foam core materials are conventionally conducted using block shaped test specimens. This works well in the linear elastic

range, but for higher stress levels strongly localised plasticity and cell crushing dominates the strongly heterogeneous deformation and progressive damage processes, thus making it difficult to provide a physically meaningful ‘homogenised’ interpretation of the material behaviour. To circumvent this Wierzbicki et al. [4] used a tapered foam specimen to obtain a local stress-strain curve.

In this study, a waist shape (WS) has been selected to obtain a ‘homogenised’ compressive stress-strain curve for the foam material. The specimen shape and dimensions are shown in Fig. 2. The specimen thickness was 15 mm, and a 14 mm × 10 mm rectangular area (square hatched in the Fig. 2) was selected as the ‘region of interest’ (ROI) to measure the strain field using digital image correlation (DIC). The specimens were milled in the through-thickness (TT) and in-plane (IP) directions from a 60 mm thickness foam sheet.

Fig. 2: Waist shape specimen with dimensions and indication of ‘ROI’ used for DIC measurements.

The elevated temperature tests were carried out using an Instron environmental chamber. The environmental chamber includes a window in the access door, and DIC measurements were conducted through the window on the front side of specimen. It has been established recently that DIC through the window is indeed feasible [4]. The elevated temperature test setup is illustrated in Fig. 3.

2.3 3D finite element analysis procedure

3D nonlinear Finite Element (FE) analyses have been conducted to estimate ‘correction factors’ that are used to compensate for the difference between the measured surface strain field and the inhomogeneous strain field over the specimen gauge section. The real physical behaviour of cross-linked PVC foams would involve both elastic, viscoelastic and plastic deformations, but it is assumed here that the elastic and plastic residual deformations under the specific test conditions exceed the viscoelastic

deformations under quasi-static testing conditions. The nonlinear FE analyses have been conducted using the FE code ABAQUS 6.12. Both geometric and material nonlinearity were included; the latter through the use of Hill’s anisotropic yield plasticity model. The nonlinear FE approach includes an iterative solution procedure, which is used to ‘correct’ the material model in the FE analyses until convergence of the derived ‘FE correction factor’ is achieved.

Fig. 3: Elevated temperature test setup using improved MAF and DIC system.

A flowchart of the approach adopted for correcting the experimentally obtained compression stress-strain curves is shown in Fig. 4. Tensile and shear through-thickness (TT) and in-plane (IP) elastic data from previous work [2] as well as experimentally obtained TT and IP direction compressive moduli were used to define input orthotropic material model for TT and IP compressive foam models. After correction of both the TT and IP compression strains, the iterative procedure was repeated until the

difference between the compression strain values in both directions (TT and IP) obtained in the last iteration (iteration n) and the previous iteration (n-1) became smaller than 0.1%. Convergence of the derived “correction factor” was achieved after typically 3-5 iterations for each model. The ‘FE correction factor’ is then used to ‘correct’ the stress-strain response measured on the ROI to obtain the average strain on the whole gauge section.

Fig. 4: flowchart of FE correction procedure adopted for correcting the experimentally obtained tensile stress-strain curves.

3 Results

3.1 Stress-strain response in compression and core crushing

Fig. 5 shows the resulting ‘corrected’ compressive stress-strain curve for Divinycell H100 tested in the ‘through-thickness’ (TT) direction at 70°C. After an initially linear region up to a peak stress (collapse

stress), the curve reveals a sudden drop in stress which is initiated by buckling of the foam cell walls [5]. The stress drops to an almost constant value (plateau stress) that does not change with increasing strain before local high strain bands (an average strain equal to 0.2-0.25 on ROI area) start to develop locally. The DIC images show the development of these local high strain bands which are associated with extensive plastic deformations and core cell crushing.

Fig. 5: Compressive behavior of H100 PVC foam in TT direction at 70°C and associated DIC images at various strain levels.

Fig. 6 shows magnified images of a part of the specimen about five cells width where the localised bands of high strain initiated. It is seen that the formation of the high strain band is associated with large deformation of a chain of cells.

Fig. 6: Magnified images of foam cells in band during compression test (red highlighted); (a): image just before starting of cell collapse, (b): crushed band of cells, (c): schematic single cell before collapse, and (d): schematic of cell during plastic collapse showing plastic bending in the cell walls.

Fig. 6a shows an intact highlighted row of cells just before the collapse load. The compression loading on the axially loaded vertical walls initiated elastic buckling in a cell wall with high slenderness ratio (thickness to height of cell wall). After buckling of one cell wall and the associated loss of local stiffness, the load on the neighbouring cell walls increased and buckling occurred, which again induced higher loads on the adjacent cell walls leading to progressing cell wall buckling and plastic collapse across a vertical band. Fig. 6b shows the chain of cells shown in Fig. 6a after collapse has occurred. It is observed that the cells above and below the collapse band are intact. Fig. 6c and 6d provides a schematic illustration of a single cell in the chain/band before and after collapse. The post mortem examination of this and other compression specimens revealed no indication that cracking cell wall fracture occurred in the collapse process. After folding of the cell walls and development of a band of crushed cells across the width of specimen, local densification increases the stiffness and load transfer capability across the specimen section. When this load becomes higher than buckling load of the intact cells, one or more new elastic buckling events occur in the intact area of the specimen adjacent to the first band of crushed/collapsed cells, and progressive crushing continues until densification of all foam specimen cells and locking has occurred. In this investigation all the compressive tests were stopped at a strain level of about 20% well before densification and increase of stress leading to final compression failure occurred.

3.2 Stress-strain response as a function of temperature

The stress-strain response of Divinycell H100 has been determined for both the TT and IP directions at five different temperatures: 23, 40, 55, 70 and 85°C. A MATLAB code was used to fit a surface to the experimentally obtained stress as a function of measured strain and temperature. The fitted surfaces were produced using a cubic spline interpolation technique. Fig. 6 shows the surface fitting to the experimental data for the TT (Fig. 6a) and IP directions (Fig. 6b), respectively. The blue circle points indicate the experimentally obtained stress-strain curves at the different temperatures. The

trends observed from Figs. 6a and 6b demonstrate that both Young's modulus in compression, and the peak stress reduce significantly with increasing temperature in both the TT and IP directions.

Fig. 6: Surface fitting of experimental stress-strain curves from 23°C room temperature to 85°C; (a): TT direction, and (b): IP direction.

A simplified model of the compressive stress-strain response based on the achieved data is shown in Fig. 7a indicating the important model parameters. The normalized curves of collapse and plateau stresses are presented in Fig. 7b, and the variation of the collapse and plateau strains are indicated in Fig. 7c using a single common curve. The dependency of

temperature of all the normalized curves for the model parameters are shown in Fig 7d.

Fig.7: Simplified compressive stress-strain curve model and parameter variations as function of temperature ; (a): schematic model and parameters, (b): Normalized curves of collapse and plateau stresses, (c): normalized curve of collapse and plateau strains, and (d): all normalized thermal curves for model parameters.

It is observed that the Young's modulus (compression) and the collapse and plateau stresses decrease with increasing temperature, whereas the collapse and plateau strains (ϵ_{clps} & ϵ_{pltu}) increase significantly at temperatures above 70°C.

4 Conclusions

A new modified Arcan fixture (MAF) has been developed to characterize lightweight polymer foam materials with respect to their tensile, compressive, shear and bidirectional mechanical properties at room temperature and at elevated temperatures. In this paper the focus has been on the characterisation of polymer foam core materials loaded in

compression. The Moreover main concluding results of the present work are summarized as follows:

- The MAF was used to characterize the anisotropic behaviour of Divinycell PVC H100 foam in compression at room and elevated temperatures. A test setup using thermal chamber and Digital Image Correlation (DIC) was used for the tests.
- A waist block (WS) specimen was developed to promote the development of a localised core cell crush band in the specimen gauge section. The results were used to determine the local true compression stress-strain curve of the polymer foam material at different temperatures.

- 3D FE analysis was used to derive correction factors that were used to correct the measured surface strain field to calculate the average strain occurring on specimen gauge section.
- Corrected compressive stress-strain curves for Divinycell PVC H100 were derived for temperatures in the range between 23 and 85°C in the core material through-thickness and in-plane directions.
- The compression properties of Divinycell PVC H100 foam including Young's modulus, collapse stress/strain, and plateau stress/strain presented at room temperature as well as temperature dependent formulations of these properties in the form of a series of polynomial equations.

The results presented briefly herein comprise a brief summary of the research presented in Taher et al. [6,7].

Acknowledgements

The work presented was co-sponsored by the Danish Council for Independent Research | Technology and Production Sciences (FTP), Grant Agreement 274-08-0488, "Thermal Degradation of Polymer Foam Cored Sandwich Structures", and the US Navy, Office of Naval Research (ONR), Grant Award N000140710227. The ONR programme manager was Dr. Yapa D. S. Rajapakse. The financial support received is gratefully acknowledged.

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